

ПЕДАГОГІЧНА АКАДЕМІЯ:
НАУКОВІ ЗАПИСКИ

ПЕДАГОГІЧНА ОСВІТА

УДК 378.633.018.43:004.78

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14344216>

**Distance learning: advantages and disadvantages in the context of modern
education**

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Прийнято: 19.11.2024 | Опубліковано: 29.11.2024

Annotation. This article discusses modern forms of distance learning that are driven by the social needs of the world and provide a wide range of opportunities for all people, regardless of their social status. In this way, the human rights to education and knowledge are realized. With the increasing challenges facing society, such as pandemics and mass invasions, the role of ICT and the introduction of online learning and distance education has become extremely important, as many educational institutions have long supported online versions of training modules. However, distance learning is still at an early stage of its life cycle. Distance learning now offers great potential for creating a system of collective learning and global information exchange, regardless of time and space constraints. The distance learning system ensures equal access to education regardless of the place of residence, health status, elitism and physical security of a person in any part of the country, thus ensuring the realization of the human right to education and knowledge. This system is able to respond to the needs of society in the most convenient and flexible way and ensure the realization of the constitutional right to education for every citizen of the country, and

based on the above factors, distance education can be considered the most effective system for training highly qualified specialists. The purpose of this study is to obtain information about students' attitudes towards distance education and to study the feasibility of its implementation. The methods of the study are theoretical analysis, generalization of literature sources, methodology and method of questioning. Results of the study. A survey was conducted among full-time students, which revealed the interest and readiness of students for distance learning, which allows us to explore the possibility of using such a system. Most students have no difficulty working with ICT and have access to high-speed Internet, which opens up great opportunities for distance learning. This learning attracts students with a variety of activities, such as watching lectures, completing written assignments, taking online exams and quizzes. Conclusions. A large number of students show interest in this type of learning, which is a strong argument in favor of introducing distance learning. Elements of distance learning can successfully complement classroom instruction, improve the quality of information technology-based education, and create conditions for accelerating the acquisition of advanced knowledge.

Keywords: distance education, high-speed Internet, the latest achievements of information and telecommunication technologies.

Дистанційне навчання: переваги та недоліки в контексті сучасної освіти

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Анотація. У цій статті розглядаються сучасні форми дистанційного навчання, які зумовлені соціальними потребами світу і надають широкий спектр можливостей для всіх людей, незалежно від їхнього соціального статусу. Таким

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чином реалізуються права людини на освіту та знання. Зі зростанням викликів, що постають перед суспільством, таких як пандемії та масові вторгнення, роль ІКТ та впровадження онлайн-навчання і дистанційної освіти стала надзвичайно важливою, оскільки багато навчальних закладів вже давно підтримують онлайн-версії навчальних модулів. Однак дистанційне навчання все ще перебуває на ранній стадії свого життєвого циклу. Дистанційне навчання зараз пропонує великий потенціал для створення системи колективного навчання та глобального обміну інформацією, незалежно від часових і просторових обмежень. Система дистанційного навчання забезпечує рівний доступ до освіти незалежно від місця проживання, стану здоров'я, елітарності та фізичної захищеності людини в будь-якій частині країни, забезпечуючи таким чином реалізацію права людини на освіту і знання. Ця система здатна найбільш зручно і гнучко реагувати на потреби суспільства і забезпечувати реалізацію конституційного права на освіту для кожного громадянина країни, а виходячи з вищезазначених факторів, дистанційну освіту можна вважати найбільш ефективною системою підготовки висококваліфікованих фахівців. Метою даного дослідження є отримання інформації про ставлення студентів до дистанційної освіти та вивчення доцільності її впровадження. Методами дослідження є теоретичний аналіз, узагальнення літературних джерел, методика та метод анкетування. Результати дослідження. Було проведено опитування серед студентів денної форми навчання, при цьому виявлено зацікавленість та готовність студентів до дистанційного навчання, що дозволяє дослідити можливість використання такої системи. Більшість студентів не мають труднощів у роботі з ІКТ та мають доступ до високошвидкісного Інтернету, що відкриває широкі можливості для дистанційного навчання. Це навчання приваблює студентів різноманітними видами діяльності, такими як перегляд лекцій, виконання письмових завдань, складання онлайн іспитів та вікторин. Висновки. Велика кількість студентів

виявляє інтерес до такого типу навчання, що є вагомим аргументом на користь запровадження дистанційного навчання. Елементи дистанційного навчання можуть успішно доповнити аудиторні заняття, підвищити якість освіти на основі інформаційних технологій та створити умови для прискорення засвоєння передових знань.

Ключові слова: дистанційна освіта, швидкісний Інтернет, новітні досягнення інформаційно-телекомунікаційних технологій.

Problem statement. The economic, political and social changes taking place in Ukraine make it necessary to accelerate the reform of the education system. The basis of socio-economic development of the information society is based on the production of information and knowledge. The development of high technologies increases the demand for the intellect of the general population of any country. This fundamentally changes the state of the education system in society and its institutional status.

Modern society needs massive quality education that can meet the increased demands on consumers and producers of material and spiritual values. Even rich countries cannot satisfy the social needs of society by increasing the budget and the number of educational institutions through other traditional means. The modernization of the education system is most clearly expressed in the concept of distance learning, which has become a major factor in its development.

Modern information technologies open up new horizons for improving the efficiency of the educational process. Active learning, self-study, and distance learning programs play an important role in this process. Distance learning is one of the forms and methods of education, defined as an individual process in which the acquisition of knowledge, skills, abilities and cognitive methods of human cognitive activity is carried out mainly through indirect interaction between remote participants of the educational process in a specialized environment, based on psychological and

pedagogical methods and modern information and communication technologies. Distance education has existed for fifty years, but over time, educational technologies have evolved due to the transfer of information and the emergence of new information networks. Today, for example, some form of distance education is offered in almost every university in the world [5].

Firstly, distance learning is an open educational system that involves active communication between a teacher and a student using modern technologies and multimedia. This type of education offers the freedom to choose where, when and how to study.

Distance learning has many advantages and significantly expands the range of potential students. Young people can benefit who cannot combine study and work or live far away: from the military to a housewife; from a business manager to a student, all who want to study in parallel. Distance learning form of education is suitable for almost everyone, because it allows you to harmoniously to combine study and everyday life in a harmonious way. Modern education requires you to constantly to expand their perception of the complexity of the world and the formation of the information society. In order for knowledge to be linked to action, it is necessary to constantly with actions, it is necessary to constantly “teach yourself”, replenishing and expanding your education. This is the goal of distance education [3].

Today, distance learning offers great potential for creating collaborative teaching and learning systems. Information exchange, regardless of time and space zones. In addition, distance learning systems provide equal opportunities for education regardless of the place of residence, health and physical safety of a person in any part of the country and abroad, in order to realize the human right to education and knowledge [4]. It is this system that can best and most flexibly respond to the needs of society and at the same time ensure the realization of the constitutional right to education for every citizen of the country. Based on the above factors, it can be

concluded that distance learning is the most effective system for training highly qualified specialists [2]. At the present stage, distance learning technology (educational process) is a set of methods and means of teaching and administration of educational procedures that ensure the distance learning process based on the use of modern information and telecommunication technologies. When implementing distance learning, information technology should ensure:

- presentation of the main volume of the product;
- interaction between students and teachers in the learning process;
- the opportunity for students to work independently to master the studied material;
- assessment of knowledge and skills acquired by students in the learning process [5].

The following information technologies can be used to achieve this goal:

- sending the materials to be studied via computer telecommunications;
- discussions and seminars held via computer telecommunications;
- online broadcasting of training programs;
- e-mail;
- video and teleconferences;
- video broadcasting with feedback;
- electronic (computer) educational resources [6].

Today, elements of distance learning successfully complement traditional classroom training. And while the structure of traditional education includes an educational institution, a teacher, a student, and material, the structure of modern distance education, in addition to the above components, includes a learning management system (a system for managing the educational environment and content) and a specialist who maintains this system. The developers of distance education believed that distance education clearly demonstrates the characteristics of a personally

oriented learning medium, so they define the individuality of learning behavior as follows:

Flexibility – a distance learning student can plan the time, place, and duration of classes.

For modules – course materials are presented in the form of modules,

Thus, the student can create an educational path, his trajectory in accordance with his potential needs and abilities. Accessibility - independence of the geographical and temporal location of the student and the educational institution does not allow restrictions on the educational needs of the country's population.

Economic efficiency is manifested in reducing costs for maintaining and reserving premises, educational institutions and various resources.

Mobility – effective implementation of feedback between the teacher and the student is one of the most important requirements and reasons for the success of the organizational development process. Simultaneous access of several students to several sources of educational information: (electronic libraries, databases, etc.).

Technology – the use of the latest ICT achievements in the educational process.

Social equality – equal opportunities for obtaining education regardless of the student's place of residence, health status, elitism and material security.

Global – export and import of world achievements in the educational services market [1].

It should be recognized that the development and implementation of distance education is complicated by some significant problems. These include, first of all, the imperfection of the regulatory framework for the organization and functioning of the distance education system. The next are technical and technological reasons, for example, the lack of connection to a high-speed Internet network or low speed of access to it, which makes it difficult to implement video conferencing and even downloading educational material. Technological problems include the lack of a mechanism for

compiling didactic materials and the absence of clear criteria for monitoring and evaluating the quality of knowledge received by distance learners. We can also note the need for a number of individual psychological conditions, such as strict self-discipline. The lack of face-to-face communication between the student and the teacher, the lack of frequent opportunities to express their knowledge orally, the predominant influence of the written basis of learning and the lack of practical knowledge are also quite important barriers. Nevertheless, distance learning has long been a reality and is a promising direction in the organization of a highly developed, well-organized and publicly accessible system that implements a huge number of educational programs of various levels in almost all areas of knowledge [3].

The purpose of the study is to obtain information about students' attitudes towards distance learning and to identify opportunities for its implementation.

Harrison, DR, and Kanuka, H. and developed educational technologies and investigated blended learning. The authors considered the possibilities of blended learning to improve distance learning, but did not pay enough attention to the social aspect of student interaction [7]. Morrison, D. in his works showed that the low level of student achievement is a serious problem, but did not single out effective strategies for solving this issue [14]. Kebrichi, M., Lipschutz, A., and Santiago, L. the authors note that student satisfaction with distance learning affects their achievement, but the reasons that lead to dissatisfaction were not identified [10]. Bernard, RM emphasizes the effectiveness of distance learning, but he does not consider long-term studies for students in this format [2]. Zhou, M. in his article emphasizes the digital divide, but does not offer solutions to overcome it [22]. Kukulska-Hulme, A., & Shield, L. scholars emphasize mobile learning, but they do not indicate the difficulties that students have with access to technology [11]. Martin, F., Sunley, R. authors note in the article the importance of community, but do not decide how it can be created in the conditions of distance learning [13]. In their current study, Ferguson, R. and Clough, D. develop

issues of sustainable development, but do not consider the environmental aspects of resource use of distance technologies [5]. Huang, RH studied student perceptions as a result of distance learning, but the mechanisms of their formation remain unclear [9]. Authors Heggart, K.R. and Yu-Li, E. confirm the effectiveness of online learning, but do not indicate specific methods for evaluating results [8].

Issues that remain unaddressed include:

- reasons for low engagement with and dissatisfaction with distance learning among students;
- strategies for bridging the digital divide and accessing distance learning technologies;
- methods for building community in an online environment.

The *purpose of this study* is to obtain information about students' attitudes towards distance education and to study the feasibility of its implementation. Further, to study student interaction during distance learning and its long-term impact on learning outcomes and academic performance.

Research methods. Theoretical analysis and generalization of scientific and methodological literature, questionnaire method.

Results of the study. In the course of our study, we conducted a survey of full-time students. Identification of students' interest and readiness for distance learning will reveal the need to develop such a system. In the course of studying the relevance of implementing distance learning, 71% of the students of the department (71 students out of 100) were interviewed. As a result, the following data were obtained. First of all, we were interested in students' readiness to use new computer technologies in the educational process. One of the indicators of this issue is the level of computer skills. Respondents were asked to rate themselves on a 10-point system.

As we can see, a large number of students – 78% - estimate their level of computer proficiency to be above average, 14% rated it at exactly 5, and only 8% of respondents

believe that it is below average (4 and below). The next factor we studied was whether students had free access to high-speed Internet, which is a prerequisite for distance learning.

Access to high-speed Internet was reported by 86% of the respondents, 13% do not have such an opportunity and 1% have intermittent access to high-speed Internet. Thus, the vast majority of students have the opportunity to participate in distance learning. The next question we studied was the degree of students' awareness of distance learning.

From shows that 27% of respondents have varying degrees of experience with distance education, but it should be noted that almost half of the students have not previously been interested in this opportunity, and 24% of respondents have not heard of this form of education at all. The desire of students to use elements of distance education while studying at the department at the academy was studied in several areas: the convenience of using lectures via high-speed Internet, the convenience of receiving academic assignments via the Internet, the convenience of taking tests via the Internet.

Evaluation of the convenience of using elements of distance learning In general, students have a positive attitude to the opportunities provided by distance education: 51% of respondents noted the convenience of viewing lectures on the Internet, 62-63% noted the convenience of receiving assignments and the attractiveness of taking tests and quizzes via the World Wide Web. On average, 30% of respondents consider this opportunity not always convenient, and about 8.5% of students are not attracted to this means of work at all, 14% said they found it difficult to answer. The students' own interest in this type of educational service may play a role.

Shows that 48% of respondents noted their interest in this type of education, about 13% of them see it as a second (additional) education, 14% of respondents are not interested in this form of education, and 24% said they were not sure. Thus, the majority of students are interested in implementing this technology. The study also

revealed students' opinions on the advantages and disadvantages of distance learning. Among the main advantages were time savings and convenience (34 and 31% respectively), as well as the ability to work in parallel and ease of learning. The main disadvantage, according to students, is the independence of studying materials, i.e. the lack of contact with a teacher (18%), followed by dependence on the Internet and low level of education (9% each), and then the lack of practice and receiving concise material (6% each). Some respondents also emphasized the loss of teacher's authority in this form of education, and 22% of students see no disadvantages in receiving education remotely.

Despite the rather extensive list of positive qualities of distance education, there are some drawbacks. First of all, it is difficult to Bidentification of distance students, since at the current stage of development technologies, it is quite difficult to check who is taking the exam. Higher education institutions higher education institutions that provide distance learning opportunities have found a way out of the situation out of the situation by requiring a student to attend several exams in person at higher education institution. At the same time, it is mandatory to provide documents that to prove their identity.

In addition, the low bandwidth of the electronic network during training or examination teleconferences is also a significant problem. This is a major problem. This primarily affects distance learners in small towns and cities of Ukraine.

Ukraine, who, in fact, are most suitable for distance education due to geographical distance from academic centers. An important disadvantage of distance education in Ukraine is also the lack of direct contact between the teacher (private tutor) and the distance student due to the high professional workload of the teacher. Students of foreign distance courses can receive answers to their messages in a few hours, since in countries with significant experience in implementing distance education, there are much more teachers than students. Unfortunately, the situation in Ukraine is the

opposite situation - we have a lot of people who want to get a distance education, and experienced teachers familiar with the latest technologies of distance communication technologies, are few.

One of the disadvantages of distance learning is the need for strong motivation. A distance learner has to study almost all the educational material learns almost all of the material on their own. This requires sufficient willpower, responsibility, and self-control.

Ukraine does not have a clearly defined strategy for scientific distance education. There are no relevant programs in the country either at the national or regional level. The low level of automation of society and especially the education system, the low use of network information technologies by educational institutions in network information technologies, the lack of formation of the national educational space in the network environment do not allow to realize all the possibilities for distance education.

Conclusions. The majority of students do not face any difficulties in working with information and communication technologies, and have access to high-speed Internet, which provides ample opportunities for distance learning. It is also worth noting the attractiveness for students of various types of work that distance learning can offer, among which we noted viewing lectures, receiving assignments and passing tests and quizzes via the Internet. A significant number of students show interest in this type of education, which is a strong argument in favor of introducing distance learning, the elements of which can successfully complement traditional classroom instruction, improve the quality of information technology-based education and create conditions for accelerating the implementation of advanced achievements.

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